

"Disorsion Of Collective Consciousness - About Delusions And Hallucinations"

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Abstract

Collective consciousness disorder refers to a condition characterized by noticeable shifts in the prevailing ideas and actions of a society or a group of people. In this scenario, people exhibit atypical behavior, have diminished logical thinking and reasoning capacities, and conform to the prevailing attitudes, beliefs, or inclinations of society (Castano et al., 2002). Collective consciousness disorder arises as a result of the impact of social psychological elements. These elements include the anonymity afforded by being part of a crowd, the diminished feeling of personal accountability, social engagement, and adherence to group standards. In this scenario, people may exhibit less critical thinking and base their judgments not on their judgment, but rather on the societal norms and accepted ideas.

Keywords: *Collective Consciousness Disorder, Psychology, Disorders, Consciousness Disorder, Individuals Behaving*

Introduction

Gustave Le Bon is a renowned social psychologist recognized for his notable contribution in the field of social psychology with his book titled "The Crowd: A Study of the Popular Mind". Le Bon contended that crowds had a distinct collective mentality that diverges from the cognitive framework of individuals, based on his analysis of societal conduct in densely populated settings. The notions are succinctly explained by Le How Bon as indicated below (Reicher & Hopkins, 2001).

Aim

These notions are crucial to the endeavor of comprehending social interactions, the formation of shared beliefs, and their impact on the collective thoughts and behaviors of society. Nevertheless, these notions remain contentious and are subject to discussion from many viewpoints.

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Literature Review and Argument

Collective Delusion : The Bon suggests that when people exhibit abnormal behavior and make illogical choices in a crowded setting, it might be attributed to a phenomenon known as collective delusion. When people are influenced by crowds, they may lose their capacity for rational thinking and display contradictory conduct by conforming to the prevailing attitudes, beliefs, or habits of society.

Collective Consciousness Disorder : The Bon suggests that a collective awareness condition might be identified by people's diminished feeling of personal responsibility and limited capacity for rational reasoning in a crowded setting. People may have a sense of anonymity when surrounded by a large group of individuals, which may lead to a decrease in their inclination to assume responsibility and promote careless actions.

Collective Hallucination : Le Bon contended that in situations when people congregate in densely populated settings and concentrate on a shared belief, ideal, or concept, a phenomenon known as collective hallucination might manifest. In this scenario, a significant portion of society may collectively embrace a fictitious or illusory notion, leading them to be disconnected from reality.

Le Bon's perspectives have significantly contributed to the comprehension of crowd psychology and social behavior. Nevertheless, some commentators have According to Drury and Reicher (2009), he expressed that Bon's work was too simple and that the study of crowd behavior required a more intricate analysis.

The Aside from Bon, several social psychologists and sociologists have also examined and attempted to elucidate notions such as collective delusion, collective unconsciousness, and collective hallucination. As an illustration:

Emile Durkheim, a French sociologist, conducted research on the impact of society on human cognition and behavior. He asserts that communal delusions and collective hallucinations

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emerge due to the common views and ideals of society. These commonly held ideas serve the purpose of enhancing social cohesion and bringing people together under a shared objective. Carl Jung was a renowned Swiss psychiatrist and psychoanalyst. Renowned Swiss psychologist Carl Jung established the notion of communal consciousness. According to Jung, each individual's inner consciousness is intricately linked to the profound and universal levels of the collective consciousness. The collective consciousness refers to a shared state of awareness that is influenced by universal concepts such as common symbols, mythologies, and archetypes. These ubiquitous symbols and archetypal pictures may also lead to collective hallucinations. Collective hallucination refers to the widespread occurrence of a shared impression or experience of unreality among members of a community. In this scenario, a collective of individuals may collectively have comparable hallucinations simultaneously and interpret them as diverging from objective reality (Winkielman). Collective hallucinations are often linked to universal imagery, such as shared symbols, mythologies, or archetypes. These pictures may stem from the cultural or religious ideologies of the community and might engage with a collective degree of awareness. Collective hallucinations may be impacted by elements such as social interactions among group members, collective subconscious processes, and shared belief systems (Reicher, 1996).

A Review from Historical Perspective

Several incidences of collective awareness disorder have occurred in various regions of the globe. These situations are often conveyed and understood as follows.

1. Salem Witch Trials (1692)

The Salem Witch Trials, a notorious incident, occurred in the state of Massachusetts in 1692. The incident started when a cohort of adolescent females asserted their identity as witches, subsequently resulting in widespread panic and anxiety across society. This scenario exemplifies a collective misconception and lack of awareness that arose due to the impact of

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social and psychological forces. The Salem Witch Trials may be attributed to the impact of the social, religious, and cultural circumstances prevalent at that time. The Puritan ideology and the prevalent culture of witch-hunting in the Massachusetts colony significantly influenced the unfolding of events. Witchcraft instilled significant terror and anxiety in society throughout this time, and this dread became deeply ingrained in the collective awareness of society (Karlsen, 1989).

Initially, a cohort of adolescent females displaying peculiar conduct and asserting their identity as witches had a profound influence on the rest of society. This event caused widespread panic, terror, and a pervasive sense of infectious delusion in the public psyche. Due to social contact and the influence of group dynamics, individuals developed a belief in the existence of witches and exhibited a collective inclination towards killing the accused. This occurrence exemplifies the influence of the collective unconscious processes of society. The interplay of group dynamics, belief systems, and social interactions in society may foster the development of collective delusions, which in turn can result in illogical and dangerous outcomes. Simultaneously, this tragedy highlights the repercussions of a dearth of robust leadership in society and an insufficient judicial system (Roach, 2003).

2. Dancing Plague Event (1518)

The Dancing Plague was a phenomenon that took place in Strasbourg, France around 1518 (Waller, 2008). This event is a phenomenon of collective dance frenzy that happens when a lady spontaneously begins dancing, and this behavior rapidly spreads to other individuals. The occurrence of this event may be attributed to the influence of psychological and social interaction elements.

When analyzing this event using academic and scientific terminology, it may be classified as a collective hallucination and a behavioral pandemic that happened due to a combination of several reasons. In this instance, there has been a noticeable exchange and spread of behavior and ideas among individuals (Bartholomew, 2001).

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The spontaneous dancing shown by an individual at the commencement of the event might perhaps be linked to the social and psychological stressors encountered in the present circumstances. These elements may include heightened exhaustion, psychological strain, societal expectations, apprehension, or shared unease. When an individual begins dancing and displays atypical alterations in behavior due to these causes, it may lead to interaction and social contagion when others are exposed to this activity. The Dancing Plague event exemplifies the impact of collective unconscious processes on society. It has been shown that individuals might have identical experiences at the level of collective consciousness and hence display comparable actions. Social interaction, group norms, and collective subconscious processes may have influenced the development of collective hallucinations and behavioral epidemics in this scenario (Piltz, 1995).

Several scholars have hypothesized that the Dancing Plague might have been triggered by poisoning from the *Claviceps purpurea* (ergot) fungus. Ergot is a fungal species that may develop when wheat and other cereals grow in fields. The ergot fungus produces psychotropic chemicals that may induce harmful consequences. Ergot poisoning may result in hallucinations like those induced by LSD, as well as muscular spasms, neurological difficulties, and severe health complications. Consequently, it is believed that some individuals in Dancing Plague experienced hallucinations due to the effects of ergot poisoning. Nevertheless, the available scientific evidence is insufficient to definitively establish a causal link between Dancing Plague and ergot toxicity. The assertion remains a subject of debate, and investigations are still under progress (Schaefer, 2017).

3. The Militarism Movement (1840)

The Millerite Movement refers to a religious movement that gained traction among several individuals, whereby the conviction that the Christian second coming, as prophesied by William Miller in the 1840s, will transpire between the years 1843-1844. Individuals who held this conviction started anticipating the arrival of the second coming, prompted by Miller's remarks. They proceeded to liquidate their assets and make necessary arrangements during this period.

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Nevertheless, the supporters of the movement experienced profound disappointment when the anticipated second coming failed to materialize (Brown, 1963). The Millerite Movement serves as a significant case study for analyzing the dissemination of religious ideas and expectations across society, as well as the corresponding behavioral responses of individuals. When analyzed via an academic lens, this event encompasses several components from both a psychological and social standpoint (Butler, 2008). The Millerite Movement is a manifestation of the social, cultural, and theological circumstances of the day. Religious revivals and sectarianism played a significant role in America during this time. Individuals such as William Miller sought to reform religious teachings by offering their own interpretations (Schwarz, 1989). The anticipation of the second coming may be seen as a phenomena that arose within the religious milieu of the era. The Millerite Movement centers on the profound emotional responses of individuals, including feelings of optimism, fear, and despair. The followers may have experienced immense excitement and anticipation due to their belief in the imminent arrival of the second coming. The heightened emotional intensity prompted individuals to divest their possessions and make necessary arrangements. Nevertheless, when the anticipated outcomes failed to materialize, individuals reported feelings of disillusionment and psychological distress. This episode exemplifies the impact of group dynamics. The Millerite Movement is a collective of individuals that united based on a shared set of beliefs. The dynamics inside the group, established group norms, social influence, and collective unconscious processes likely influenced the followers' engagement in this idea and their willingness to express their expectations (Butler, 2008).

The Millerite Movement encompasses both individual psychological elements and the religious and cultural milieu of the day. Individuals engaged in the anticipation of the second coming based on their own personal encounters, belief structures, and aspirations (Nichols, 1998). This exemplifies the manner in which religious convictions may intersect with one's own identity and quest for purpose. The Millerite Movement exemplifies significant cognitive processes. Individuals endeavored to bolster the anticipation of the second coming by scrutinizing accessible facts, symbolic exegesis, and prophetic utterances. This approach examines how

religious teachings might influence the perceptual and cognitive processes of humans (From, 1990).

Following the Millerite Movement, society saw significant transformations, resulting in widespread disillusionment. Several adherents experienced doubt or modified their religious convictions when their anticipated outcomes were not fulfilled. Some individuals remained involved in the movement and directed their attention into developing fresh interpretations, establishing alternative timelines, and formulating new systems of thought. The Millerite Movement made significant contributions to the examination of phenomena such as religious mania, anticipation, and disillusionment. This phenomenon has been examined in fields such as social psychology, religious anthropology, and religious studies, and has emerged as a significant case for comprehending individuals' belief systems, group dynamics, and emotional responses (Moon, 1998).

The Millerite Movement originated as a response to the prevailing theological and social circumstances of the time, including a set of beliefs and anticipations. This incident exemplifies an intricate phenomena in which religious beliefs, emotional responses, social dynamics, and cognitive processes converge.

4. OrsonWelles' " War of the Worlds " Radio Play (1938)

On October 30, 1938, Orson Welles' live radio drama "War of the Worlds" prompted some listeners to mistakenly believe in an actual extraterrestrial invasion, leading to a state of fear (Miller, 2010). This event is a significant occurrence that may be analyzed in relation to communication, media influence, and collective psychology.

Initially, the event was greatly impacted by the function of communication and media influence. During that era, radio emerged as a very popular and extensively used medium of communication, with radio broadcasts being widely regarded as a dependable source. Orson Welles' radio drama may have been mistaken for an actual news broadcast by select listeners

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due to its presentation in a certain style and structure. This phenomenon eroded the distinctions between what is genuine and what is fictional.

Furthermore, the episode was influenced by mass psychology. Several onlookers reacted to the distress and emergency calls of others in a similar fashion. The response of the general population incited widespread terror and anxiety, hence amplifying the perception that a genuine assault had taken place. This exemplifies the phenomenon of individuals being susceptible to the effect of others' actions and the overall reaction of society. Orson Welles' radio drama serves as a significant exemplar for comprehending the influence of communication instruments and media on individuals. After the occurrence, there have been conversations about media ethics and accountability. It has been stressed that radio broadcasts should clearly define the boundaries between fact and fiction (Wasko, 2010). The radio drama "War of the Worlds" by Orson Welles is a significant example for studying topics like communication, media impact, and collective psychology. This study demonstrates the impact of radio broadcasts on individuals' perceptions and responses, the need to establish clear distinctions between fact and fabrication, and the collective reactions of society.

5. Tanganyika Hornbeam Madness (1962)

The Tanganyika Hornbeam Madness refers to a collective catastrophe that took place in the Mbeya area of Tanzania in 1962 (Mwakalinga, 2013). The occurrence of this event may be elucidated via the amalgamation of psychological interplay, social influences, and cultural elements.

The occurrence of a peculiar crisis in one student at the beginning of the episode, followed by a subsequent rise in the number of other students displaying similar behavior, may be attributed to the phenomenon of social contagion or the social imitation effect. (Kucharsky, 2020). Individuals have a tendency to mimic the actions they see in their surroundings, and this inclination becomes more apparent in circumstances that are stressful or ambiguous. The proliferation of this practice may have been facilitated by the social connections and interactions among pupils. Nevertheless, there is a belief that the incidence is connected to

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cultural and societal influences. Regional customs, folklore, or cultural traditions might influence individuals to display collective behaviors under certain circumstances. The hornbeam tree itself may possess symbolic or cultural importance, hence potentially exerting an impact on individuals' behavior.

The Tanganyika Hornbeam Madness is a significant phenomenon that has been examined in the context of social psychology and social dynamics. This episode exemplifies the impact of group dynamics, social mimicry effects, and cultural elements on human behavior. The tragedy may have happened due to psychological and social stress factors. The Tanganyika Hornbeam Madness is an occurrence that has been examined from the perspectives of social psychology and community psychology. This event signifies a communal catastrophe that arose due to social interactions, cultural influences, and psychological strain. (Nunn et al., 2014).

Conclusion

The commonality among these occurrences lies in the shared occurrence of comparable illusions or hallucinations among individuals. Psychological interactions, social imitation effects, cultural variables, and society conventions all contribute to the development of these collective illusions. Furthermore, the way society reacts to elements such as stress, uncertainty, or expectations may also impact these occurrences.

Studying collective delusions is crucial for comprehending human behavior and doing research in the field of social psychology. These occurrences enhance our comprehension of human relationships, belief systems, and social dynamics. The examination of collective illusions enhances research in psychology, sociology, and communication, shedding light on the intricacies of social behavior.

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